

IR1318-16 was selected from Jin Heung/IR262-43-8-11//Calady and IR262 from Peta/Peta*2//TN1. Its short stature and yield capacity originated from TN1 and the large, translucent kernels from Calady. Jin Heung may be responsible for Calpearl's short grains and Earlirose provided earliness. Calrose 76 has cold tolerance, lodging resistance, and high grain fertility.

Calpearl yields 10 t/ha, about 10% more than the average japonica grown in California and performs well when planted late. Its grains ripen 5 or more days earlier than most japonicas (see table). It can be harvested before the October rainy season, and has 5% lower grain moisture at harvest, which saves fuel during grain drying. Calpearl is easily combine harvested.

Its only disadvantage is that its large translucent kernels closely resemble

Average yield and agronomic characteristics of California rices.

Variety ^a	Tests (no.)	Year	Yield (t/ha)	Moisture at harvest (%)	Days to 50% heading	Plant height (cm)	Percent lodging	Seedling vigor ^b	Hull type ^c
S-201 j	20	1980-84	8.9	19.7	95	89	33	4.2	S
M9 j	20	1980-84	8.4	21.6	93	94	57	4.1	S
M-201 j	20	1980-84	9.4	21.4	94	86	9	4.1	S
Calmochi-202 jg	20	1980-84	8.3	22.2	99	94	28	4.0	S
M-302 j	17	1980-84	9.0	19.9	103	94	24	4.2	S
M-401 j	17	1980-84	9.1	20.0	106	94	52	4.3	S
M7 j	17	1980-84	8.9	21.0	110	97	15	4.4	S
Calrose 76 j	12	1980-84	9.1	18.4	110	97	22	4.3	P
Calpearl j	10	1982-84	9.9	16.3	89	84	20	4.7	P
M-101 j	10	1982-84	8.7	18.7	88	86	43	4.6	S
California Belle i	9	1982-84	7.6	16.9	88	102	42	3.5	S
L-202 i	9	1982-84	9.1	18.5	95	81	3	3.6	S

^aj = japonica, g = glutinous, i = indica. ^b Subjective score: 1 = very poor, 5 = excellent. CS = smooth, P = pubescent.

those of California medium-grain rices. California's Grain Inspection Service has classified Calpearl as a medium-grained variety, but milled Calpearl rice meets

US Department of Agriculture short-grain standards. Calpearl was planted on 24% (32,376 ha) of California riceland in 1983. *ℒ*

ACK-5 for direct seeded rainfed conditions

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ACK-5 was developed from D.6-2-2/IR8 at the College of Agriculture in Kolhapur, India, and released for general cultivation in May 1985.

Performance of ACK-5 in station and adaptive trials, Kolhapur, India.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		
	1983	1984	Average
<i>Station trial</i>			
Direct seeded ^a			
ACK-5	4.7	4.9	4.8
RDN185-2	5.7	4.5	5.1
Transplanted ^b			
ACK-5	5.7	3.3	4.5
RDN185-2	4.1	3.0	3.9
<i>Adaptive trial^c</i>			
Direct seeded			
ACK-5	3.8 (10)	4.0 (14)	3.9
RDN185-2	3.4 (10)	3.4 (14)	3.4
Transplanted			
ACK-5	3.3 (3)	3.0 (23)	3.2
RDN185-2	3.4 (3)	3.0 (23)	3.2

^a Mean of 2 locations. ^b Mean of 3 replications. ^c Numbers in parentheses indicate number of locations.

The semidwarf can be grown direct seeded in rainfed conditions, or transplanted. It matures in 120-125 d when direct seeded and in 110-115 d when transplanted. Grains are short and bold (length: breadth 2.25) without white belly. Cooking quality and taste are acceptable and it has 8.8% crude protein. Recovery is 65% with hulling, 60% with milling, and 54% head rice. Flaked rice is better than that of local varieties.

ACK-5 was evaluated for 8 yr under upland conditions. It yielded

significantly higher than several local varieties. Performance in direct seeded and transplanted station and adaptive trials is compared with that of popular, short-duration RDN185-2 (HS-17/TN1) in the table. ACK-5 yield potential is 4 to 6 t/ha. It yielded 4.9 t/ha in direct-seeded trials in 1984, and 5.7 t/ha in transplanted trials in 1983.

ACK-5 is moderately susceptible to blast but is tolerant of Fe chlorosis and drought stress. It has 20 d seed dormancy. *ℒ*

Katrin: a new rice variety for Tanzania

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IET2397, a strain developed in India, was released as Katrin for general cultivation in Tanzania. A derivative of HR19/2x IR8, Katrin is semidwarf (90 cm), resistant to blast and lodging, photoperiod sensitive, and has medium duration (135 d). Average yield is 5.6 t/ha. Grains are long, slender, and

translucent white with good cooking quality. Amylose content is 30%. Grain length-breadth ratio is 3.43, and volume expansion is 4.2. Fifty percent flowering is achieved in 102 d. It produces about 10 panicles/hill and 1,000-grain wt is 30 g. *ℒ*

CR666, the 60-day rice strains

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CR666 (Sattari/Rasi/Kalinga III) lines